

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

The concept of the textbook modernization in the era of information technologies: physical education and challenges of modernity

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Abstract

This paper presents the search for solutions for the modernization of textbooks on physical culture. Technological progress is gaining momentum every day, making yesterday's advanced solutions obsolete today. Such challenges require a number of measures on updating the manuals and the entire teaching process. In the paper, we analyzed the available textbooks for high school students: as a result, we discovered the problem of the course content itself, which could not meet the needs of the modern information society or fulfill the tasks that were set in the Federal Law for physical culture. Thanks to this study, we were able to identify the students' key needs in knowledge related to physical education, as well as to understand what format of material presentation is currently the most effective. We considered a completely different approach not only to the learning process itself, but also proposed a conceptually new model of a training manual on the subject, which, in our opinion, cannot consist of just a textbook today.

The text format is necessary, but only as a kind of base for a course, while the main tools should correspond to the level of technological progress. That is, a modern textbook should be a set of certain tools that contribute to better mastering the material, and this can be achieved only by taking into account the current trends in information dissemination. This paper is devoted to the definition and implementation of these tools in the educational process.

Keywords: physical culture, information society, teacher-manager, modernization of education.

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Introduction

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According to Federal Law No. 329-FZ of 04.12.2007 (as amended on 30.12.2020), physical culture is a part of culture that includes a certain set of values, norms and knowledge that contribute to the physical and intellectual development of human abilities. All this is achieved through the improvement of their motor activity and a healthy lifestyle formation, as well as social adaptation through physical education, physical training and development. While physical education, according to the definition given in the same Federal Law, is "a process aimed at educating the individual, developing the personal physical capabilities, acquiring skills and knowledge in the sphere of physical culture and sports in order to form a fully developed and physically healthy person with a high level of physical culture."

Based on this, we can conclude that physical culture, as a subject, should be one of the key disciplines in secondary and higher schools curricula, since the main field of its activity is human health. However, after analyzing the students and schoolchildren's attitude to physical education, the opposite picture appears. People who have taken a physical education course call it "useless" and "inapplicable to life", expressing an extremely low level of interest in this subject. At the same time, the need to search for and gain knowledge about health remains at a fairly high level (Shalabodina, Stradze, 2020; Shalabodina, 2019; Hickson, 2003). Accordingly, the root of the problem lies either in the content of the subject or in the competencies of the people who teach it (Bronikowski, 2010). First of all, we decided to pay attention to the content of textbooks for high school students.

As an example, we considered three textbooks for grades 10-11. For example, in the textbook by A. P. Matveev and E. S. Palekhova (2019), general information about the benefits of physical culture and sports was presented, and almost every topic had a historical digression, giving a broader idea of the subject under consideration. Attention is paid to the "Ready for Labour and Defense" standards, various functional tests are considered. Practical recommendations are given for the independent construction of a training session, as well as for the implementation of health and recovery procedures. In the third chapter, the techniques of performing various gymnastic complexes and some sports games are analyzed in detail.

G. I. Pogadaev's textbook (2019) considers safety rules for practicing various physical activities, various training complexes, in general terms, without explaining how these classes can affect the human body. The main part of the textbook is devoted to individual sports disciplines' techniques.

V. I. Lyakh's textbook (2019) also demonstrated an emphasis on the theoretical aspects of physical culture impact on a person, but in most cases, superficial explanations were given of the correlation between the body state and the degree of this impact. The second chapter is devoted to the analysis of the basic sports

included in the school curriculum, and the third is a practical guide to performing certain exercises independently.

Most of Lyakh's and Pogadaev's textbooks are devoted to the description of the technique of doing exercises or engaging in individual sports disciplines. In this comparison, Matveev and Palekhova's textbook (2019) looks preferable, but it also pays 50% of the total material to this component. With this approach, after reading the textbook, students will at best have an idea of how to pass certain standards, which is unlikely to increase their level of physical activity culture. The book can also create the prerequisites for a positive attitude to the subject of physical culture. In addition, people who have read only one paragraph about the dangers of smoking or even the entire chapter about the usefulness of daily physical activity can not be required to take a conscious approach to their health, they simply do not have time to form it consciously (Bronikowski, 2010).

To create a foundation for such a culture formation, it is necessary to purposefully influence the students' consciousness, to explain to them the cause-and-effect correlation between health, their condition and physical education. Only understanding what a particular action should be performed for can encourage a person to do it of their own free will, to take steps for self-development and self-education (Lukyanenko, 2007).

Analyzing the content of the textbooks under consideration, we can conclude that they do not teach what students really need. After completing the school program, they completely lack knowledge about proper nutrition, breathing, they do not understand that physical activity is not only standards or gymnastics; they do not know anything about their body functioning. Such ignorance is a significant problem, since it forms an incorrect attitude to physical culture and one's health (Shalabodina, Stradze, 2020; Hickson, Fishburne, 2001). Thanks to the existing methods, a false idea is formed that physical culture is only a discipline responsible for physical activity, which most often does not bring joyful emotions. Such a situation can be changed only by creating new modern approaches to teaching, the need for which is dictated by the modern information society realities (Lukyanenko, 2007). Such conditions force us to look not only for new teaching methods, but also to touch on new aspects of the discipline content, because the old ones have already lost their relevance (Shalabodina, Stradze, 2020; Bronikowski, 2010). Existing textbooks do not take into account the modern life peculiarities, and therefore cannot fully contribute to the motor activity culture formation and, as a result, can't form a healthy society (Lukyanenko, 2007).

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is the development of a new concept of a textbook on physical culture that meets the modern information society needs.

Literature review

Many researchers, both in Russia and abroad, touched upon the topic of physical education modernization and offered a number of conceptual approaches. A number of them saw the main problem as a consequence rather than the root cause itself, namely, the health state violation expressed in excess weight and inactivity (Chin, & Edginton, 2014). Such authors suggested ways to increase the daily level of physical activity as a solution to this problem (Kim & So, 2012; Fagaras, Radu, & Vanvu, 2015). In this case, they were talking about increasing the sports component of classes as a factor that can lead to an improvement in the overall dynamics of the healthy generation formation (Lubysheva, 2016). D. Merkel repeats the same fact in the research, in which the author proves that students who are engaged in sports demonstrate higher indicators in many parameters (increased self-esteem, suicidal behavior risk reduction, etc.) than those who are not sporty (Merkel, 2013).

A deeper approach to the problem is demonstrated by scientists whose research has focused on identifying the root causes of sedentary behavior among students (Pires, Mussi, & Silva, 2013; Roberts, Reeves, & Ryrie, 2015). They identified several factors that affect the low rates of young people's physical activity: lack of time, lack of social support and insufficient level of motivation. According to the authors, the successful implementation of state strategies in the sphere of physical culture is possible only with complex changes in the entire learning process, which includes both educational and leisure components. Yet again, the emphasis was placed on promoting a healthy lifestyle by increasing the amount of sport and entertainment programs, which hardly solved the general problem of students' non-acceptance of this subject of the educational program (Piri, Afosi, & Mazreno, 2015).

Such an emphasis on the sports component of physical education was criticized by Lukyanenko's concept (Lukyanenko, 2007). The author insisted that it is necessary for the students to achieve awareness and self-improvement desire, but this effect is almost impossible to achieve without fundamental transformations of the existing educational system. Lukyanenko sought to change the very role of the "physical culture" subject from an optional discipline to the category of fundamental and necessary not only on paper, but also due to the knowledge that students would receive in the classroom. Similar ideas can be traced in a number of other scientists' works (Stradze & Bykhovskaya, 2019; Shalabodina & Stradze, 2020).

Another component that has received special attention in the context of physical culture transformation is the teacher's role (Bronikowski, 2010). Some studies have suggested a drastic change in this role from

teacher-coach to teacher- educational process manager (Shalabodina, 2019).

In the last decade, we can also highlight another area of research related to the search for new pedagogical tools, namely, the study of social networks possibilities (Hergüner, 2011). With the development of such services, the direction of research also changed: from YouTube (one of the first platforms to prove its educational potential) to Facebook, Instagram, and others, which gained popularity later (Azer, 2012; Thalluri & Penman, 2015). One cannot but note the increased interest in this topic caused by the pandemic consequences, when people were forced to use interactive means of communication and, accordingly, find ways to conduct teaching activities in these conditions (Yuliyanto et al, 2020).

The analysis of the available research in this area allowed us to form the main provisions of our concept, which is described in the main part of this paper.

Methodology

The experimental group consisted of 162 students of the 1st-3rd year of Moscow City Pedagogical University. Our study was conducted in three stages (see Table 1).

Table 1. Research stages

1 st stage		2 nd stage	3d stage
Interviewing students		Pedagogical experiment	Creating a model
1 st unit (questionnaire)	2 nd unit (interview and voting)	Four methods were tried: 1. Using the textbook for grades 10-11 2. Using one's own training material 3. Point 2 + tutorial video 4. Point 3 + a set of tasks from social networks	To create a model of physical education modernization, taking into account the problem areas of existing physical culture teaching methods
1. To determine the students' knowledge level 2. To define the problems of low and high indexes	1. To find out the students' interests in Sports and Healthy lifestyle spheres 2. To conduct a vote to determine the most popular topics	To analyze the methods according to various performance criteria a. Interest b. Convenience c. Benefit d. Clarity e. Motivation to continue learning by this method	Problems to resolve: 1. The thematic content of the course does not meet the students' needs. 2. The teacher is absent from the information space 3. There are no clear or understandable goals that need to be achieved when learning the material

At the first stage, our goal was to determine the level of students' knowledge about their health and general issues of physical culture, as well as to identify their degree of need for such information, to determine the range of the most popular topics. For this purpose, we composed a questionnaire consisting of two units. In the first block, we asked students questions on topics that, in our opinion, were of key importance in human physical culture formation. All questions were divided into three levels of difficulty: easy, basic, and advanced. In the second block, we asked the students themselves to indicate the areas that aroused their greatest interest.

At the second stage, we tried to find out the potential of using modern information technologies in the educational process. We conducted an experiment in which the same information was presented to students in different ways. As an example, we chose the topic of the respiratory system physiology. In the first case, it was an excerpt from the current textbook, in the second case, we used our version of the text, in the third case, a video on the YouTube channel was used along with the text; in the fourth, we added several tasks from social networks. In our opinion, they should have motivated students to study the topic more deeply, as well as should have had a beneficial effect on the received information assimilation.

At the third stage, we analyzed the information received and developed a model for the physical education modernization.

Results

The first stage of the study began with the development of a questionnaire for the experimental group. The set of questions for determining the students' knowledge level included five topics: human physiology, nutrition, training process organization, adaptive physical culture and recovery process after physical activity. Each topic had 9 questions. Four easy, the correct answer in which was estimated by 1 point, three basic for 2 points each and two advanced, for which one could get 5 points. A maximum of 100 points could be obtained for five topics.

The assessment of the knowledge of students who scored from 0 to 40 points was considered "unsatisfactory", 38% of the subjects entered this group after passing the test. The level of "satisfactory" was reached by 54% of the respondents. The group "good" and "excellent" included 5% and 3% of students, respectively. A detailed graph of the results dynamics can be seen in Figure 1.

It is also interesting to see how the percentage of correct answers on the test topics was distributed, which is illustrated in Figure 2. It was noted that students gave a greater number of correct answers on topics related to nutrition, training sessions organization, as well as the body recovery after sports. Still, questions about physiology and adaptive physical culture appeared to be problematic. In the comments after the test, the students indicated that they had never had to deal with the study of human body physiology outside of the school Biology course, and they did not assume that these questions were directly related to physical culture. The respondents associated awareness of nutrition issues, training organization and recovery process with a personal interest in these topics and independent search for information. In addition, some respondents pointed to the role of personal fitness instructors who helped them in obtaining this knowledge. No one mentioned that they had received his knowledge by attending physical education at school or university.

In the second block of the questionnaire, we asked the experimental group participants to indicate topics related to sports and healthy lifestyle, which, in their opinion, should be included in the physical culture course. We collected all the options offered by the students, combined the repeated ones, and then held a vote. Everyone could choose up to five answers. The most popular answers can be seen in Figure 3. The answers that received less than 10% of the votes were not considered being the least popular and out of this work interest.

Fig. 3. The most popular topics which should be included into physical culture course (according to student's opinion)

Four out of five respondents were interested in training at home. Students noted that they do not always have the time or opportunity (lack of finances, embarrassment) to visit gyms, but they want to train, so the option with home training complexes is most preferable for them. They experienced a particular lack of knowledge in this area during the self-isolation period. The second and third places were divided between "proper nutrition" and "how to make your body beautiful?" options. In fact, both of these confirmed the modern young generation's aspiration to the healthy lifestyle ideology. Young people are motivated to gain knowledge in this area both independently and with the qualified teachers' help, which was confirmed by the results of two survey blocks. The third most popular response was the students' desire to know how to improve their health through various exercises. Many students complained of all sorts of ailments and were convinced that they would be able to level them by physical culture and sports. Yet, their knowledge in this area was insufficient, as confirmed by the first block of the questionnaire. Almost every second person said that he/she would like to know how to choose the right sports equipment. For many, the availability and variety of sporting goods was an embarrassing factor; they were afraid to buy the wrong shoes or clothes, so they wanted to know how to choose them properly. The rest did not understand the difference between different models of sneakers and did not see the need for other sports goods.

For example, the information that the use of the wrong running shoes can lead to serious health problems or that flat feet owners should wear sneakers that provide additional support and structural cushioning was brand new to them and became a catalyst for increasing the interest in this issue. Another topic that aroused the interest of a third of all respondents was the variety of physical activity types. The students wanted to know more about the sports that are less popular in our country. The key motivational component was the desire to expand their horizons and / or find something interesting and new for oneself.

The analysis of the survey helped us to form the most popular areas, as well as to point out the most

problematic topics for students in the sphere of physical culture and sports. Such results contributed to a more competent approach to the planned textbook content preparation. Having understood the content of the course, we moved on to the second stage of the study, namely, to the potential of using modern information technologies in the educational process.

For the second stage, we divided all the experimental group participants into four subgroups of 40-41 people. The division was based on the results of the first block of the questionnaire. In each of the subgroups, there was an approximately equal number of students who scored a certain number of points. All the experiment participants had to study the topic of respiratory system physiology, but the learning process for each subgroup was different. The first subgroup received an excerpt from the textbook used in high school, the second, third and fourth subgroups studied the topic with the material presented by the author of this work. The third subgroup had the opportunity to consolidate the studied topic (or, in the case of individual students, to study it for the first time) by watching the video on the YouTube channel. In the case of the fourth subgroup, we gave them additional tasks that needed to be done using social networks.

In writing the educational text, we based on several principles: structure, fullness/completeness and ease of perception. Structuralism is a clear logic of the material presentation. The next paragraph should follow the meaning of the previous one. In addition, the text should be split into subsections and include emphasis on important places, such material is much easier to read (and, accordingly, to understand) than when it is presented as a single array. Without focus and distinctions, the reading process is really tiring, because the readers' concentration decreases.

The completeness of the educational text can be estimated by what the student will receive after reading it. A specific goal must be set, so that the student understands why he/she is studying the material and what practical benefits it can bring him/her. There shouldn't be abstract goals, for example, "to become healthy": the goal should be clear and achievable, for example, "to learn to control blood pressure by breathing".

In addition, one should remember that any text should be primarily aimed at the reader. The idea of its creation is to be perceived and understood. If we are talking about students and high school pupils, it means that our target audience will be young people aged 16 to 23 years. Texts filled with excessive terminology and complex speech patterns can not be fully perceived by this category of readers, which means that they cannot fully perform the training task.

Understanding the specifics of the young audience and their involvement in the information space, we could not ignore the possibility of using social networks in the educational process. We developed several types of tasks that were supposed to combine both entertaining, communicative (something that encourages students to

go to social networks) and the educational function.

The first type of task is challenges. They are aimed more at mass participation and drawing attention to a particular action. Doing something like this, a person remembers it as a vivid impression, which favorably affects the general attitude to the subject under study. An additional effect is imposed by the peculiar "virality" of this phenomenon. When we see that several people perform some action, we subconsciously volunteer to repeat it. In our case, we offered students to participate in the challenge "oxy-pause or let the whole world wait". The essence of it was that students had to post a photo in the story on their page, where they would sit with the correct posture and meditate on some interesting background, as well as to mark it with the appropriate hashtag. With the help of this challenge, we tried to draw the students' attention to the technique of regulated breathing, "oxy-pause".

The second version of the tasks was live broadcasts, where we conducted 15-20 minutes of stretching training with the inclusion of breathing exercises. A significant advantage of live broadcasts is that video recordings are saved on the page during the day, i.e. if a person could not connect online, he/she will be able to work out on their own at the convenient time.

The third type of task was creative. It was necessary to put a post in the main feed on your page and tell about some little-known fact on the topic, starting with the phrase "Do you know that...?". It could be an attention-grabbing photo or an interesting video created by the student. The main emphasis was on creativity and the ability to briefly convey important information to others. The key indicator of successful completion of the task was the number of comments and "like" marks under the post.

We focused on evoking the reaction of the students' community, because we understood that many of them treat their personal pages as their business cards. With this attitude, people can't afford to post low-quality content, because they try to please others or tell something crucial about themselves or their interests. With this task, we wanted to combine the students' desire to show their best side, their ability to search for and process the necessary information, as well as the wish to be appreciated by others.

At the end of the experiment, we asked the students to evaluate the methods used in their training, based on the following criteria: interest, convenience, usefulness, clarity, motivation to continue learning. The students evaluated each of the items on a ten-point scale. The average ratings are given in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Average rating of the methods according to the suggested criteria

Criteria	Interest	Convenience	Usefulness	Clarity	Motivation
Method "A" textbook for grades 10-11	2,9	4,3	5,7	4,1	1,8
Method "B", the authors' text	5,3	4,5	6,8	6,9	4,7
Method "C" authors' text + video	7,5	8,1	8,2	8	8,4
Method "D" authors' text + video+ tasks in social nets	7,7	7,1	8,5	7,7	8,5

The "A" method, in which students were required to learn the material using a high school textbook, received the lowest scores on all criteria. The students showed no interest in such a presentation and, as a result, were not motivated to continue their studies. When we replaced the educational text with the one developed in accordance with our principles (method "B"), it approximately doubled the students' interest and motivation, it also affected the other criteria, though not so significantly. The key factor in increasing all indicators was the addition of educational video content (methods "C" and "D").

Students noted the convenience of mastering the material with the help of video, since they could watch or listen to it anywhere (in particular in the subway), which greatly saved time. In addition, the video increased

the interest in the subject among those students who usually spend not so much effort on studying, ignoring the recommendations in reading textbooks. In the case of "D" method, when additional tasks were given in social networks, it can be noted that for those students who did not use social networks as the main reason for using the mobile phone (~15% of the experimental subgroup), this caused some discomfort. However, for the others, this served as an additional incentive, increasing their interest and motivation to study the topic. In this case, the students stopped seeing the teacher as incompetent and ignorant of modern information trends, which helped the teachers quickly gain their respect and find contact. Especially the students positively noted the live broadcasts, since most of them felt the need for home training, and such a format could satisfy these requests.

Discussions

Having completed the analysis of various techniques' application, we moved on to the third stage of our study. According to the results of the study, we found three main problems of the existing system of teaching physical culture:

1. The thematic content of the course does not meet the needs of students.
2. The teacher is absent from the information space.
3. There are no clear and understandable goals that need to be achieved after learning the material.

We see the solution to the first problem in a complete revision of the course content. The inclusion of text instructions on how to do exercises is very inefficient, especially if they take up 50 or more percent of the volume of the entire textbook. First, such a description of training complexes looks obsolete in the technological progress era, when one can find video instructions on any topic in the Internet. Secondly, such an emphasis on the technique of doing certain exercises makes it impossible to pay due attention to more important theoretical issues. The low level of students' knowledge in this sphere, as well as their negative assessment of the subject itself, in principle, demonstrates a serious gap in physical education. In our vision of the textbook concept, theoretical information on key topics should make up the main layer of the total content, i.e. not less than 80%. It is the information obtained within the framework of studying the subject of physical culture that should be a guarantee of reliability, so that students do not look for it in dubious sources, as they do now. Thanks to the study of the students' needs, we were able to form a pool of the most popular topics (the approximate direction that a particular topic should cover is indicated in parentheses):

- Human physiology (functioning of the main body systems, influence on them through physical

activity);

- Nutrition (proper nutrition as the foundation of human health, sports nutrition);
- Healthy activity (adaptive physical culture, physical activity for those who have a sedentary lifestyle);
- Activity for beauty (how to remove extra pounds or gain muscle mass, training in the gym, outside and at home);
- Sports equipment: choose wisely (selection of sports clothing and shoes for different types of physical activity);
- Sports and outdoor activities: from running and swimming to dancing and nordic walking (introducing different types of physical activity).

It is important to note that educational videos should accompany the text on each topic. A modern textbook on physical culture cannot exist without it. Otherwise, it loses its effectiveness by more than 2-3 times. It is impossible to explain what softball looks like on paper or in words, especially if the explaining person has never done it. The same applies to the instructions for performing individual exercises. The video saves time, expands opportunities and increases the efficiency of the educational process.

Here we gradually move on to the second designated problem, namely, the teacher's absence in the information space. A physical education teacher should be a healthy lifestyle promoter; his/her task is to motivate as many students as possible to take up physical activity. At the moment, the universal propaganda tool is social networks. The younger generation is completely immersed in this environment and perceives popular bloggers as idols to worship. Young people are not affected or very modestly influenced by adults, if their beliefs are not pronounced in a video on YouTube or Instagram. Such dependence has created a demand for the appearance of educational and motivational content in the sphere of health, proper nutrition and sports in social networks, where fitness centers, coaches and individual athletes have long joined. Yet, unlike the listed categories that are viewed from the screens, the teacher is a real person whom the students are familiar with, and it distinguishes him from other bloggers.

In addition, we can not be sure of the popular blog posts information's reliability, unless, of course, we were not involved in its compilation. If we want to influence the young people's opinion, then teachers must occupy this niche. Here, to occupy it does not mean just to create an account in one of the popular

social networks, it means to fill it with competitive content. A page in a social network is a business card, according to which people evaluate the owner and make conclusions about whether a person is worthy of attention or not. If this attention is not captured, then all attempts to exert mass influence on young people will fail, because they will be broken by the belief that you are old-fashioned, incompetent and do not know anything about modern trends. In addition, social networks create amazing opportunities for using new types of tasks in the course, which can help students express themselves in their natural information environment. It might also help the teacher to gain the students' respect and win their favor. Therefore, together with the theoretical text and video material, the teacher should have a blog in social networks as an additional tool that expands his/her capabilities and is the only possible way to really influence the younger generation.

Still even if we provide a full-fledged theoretical course and launch a blog in social networks, all this will not have the desired effect until we eliminate the third problem, namely the lack of clear and understandable goals to be achieved by passing the material. During the course, students should clearly understand why they are doing this, and at the end of the course, they should be able to apply the skill in practice. Physical education is a very practice - oriented discipline, because the knowledge gained on it is directly related to the person's life and health. If the teacher does not manage to build an understanding of this correlation in his students, then even the most motivated of them will not be instilled in physical culture in the sense that is prescribed in the Federal Law. Each topic should be justified by the need to apply this knowledge in the future. In this case, the teacher is not just a guide of knowledge and a motivator, but a kind of the educational process manager; and like any competent manager, he/she must create the conditions for the system to work with maximum productivity.

A modern physical education teacher's effectiveness indicator will be an empty gym during class hours, since all his students have found a sports section according to their desires and needs. Yet, this goal will not be achievable as long as the task of physical culture as a subject is considered to be the sports standards implementation instead of forming a personality. Such an attitude is detrimental to the very essence of physical culture. Therefore, the role of the teacher-manager is of key importance in the concept of a new approach to physical education. One can provide a great theoretical course on the subject, supplement it with interesting video material, and even launch a popular blog, but this will not bring results if the teacher is not able to set the right goals and objectives for his/her students.

Conclusion

In our understanding, the modern approach to creating a textbook cannot be based solely on one subject

textbook, even if this textbook meets the social requirements for the proper educational content. A modern textbook should be a set of tools that includes a textbook, educational video material, as well as a teacher's blog in social networks. Existing textbooks do not solve the tasks set, so they need to be updated, not only in their content. The video content addition to each of the topics under consideration has to become mandatory. In addition, clear cases on the use of social networks in teaching should be developed. Social networks are an amazing tool for influencing people, if we want to draw the young people's attention to the issues of their health and physical activity culture, we must go out into this space; otherwise our efforts will not bring the desired effect. The teacher's role in this case will change from the teacher-coach, which we can see now, to the teacher-manager, who is able to organize the educational process in such a way that he/she could contribute to the formation of a healthy society, which is the very essence of Physical culture as a subject.

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